

TEACHERS VS. AI-BASED CLASSES IN EDUCATION: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS AND FUTURE PROSPECTS

Shakhnoza Mamatova Hoshim qizi

Karshi Irrigation and Agrotechnologies Institute

shaxnozamamatova97@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This article explores the role of teachers in education in comparison to AI-based classes. It examines the differences and similarities between the two approaches, highlighting their advantages and disadvantages. The article also explores the prospects of teachers and AI-based classes in the future and provides practical examples of their usage.

KEY WORDS: *teachers, AI-based classes, education, role, comparison, advantages, disadvantages, prospects, personal interaction, emotional intelligence, adaptability, pedagogical expertise, personalized learning, self-discipline, accessibility, flexibility, data-driven insights, scalability, cost-effective, blended learning, integration, harmonious, student-centered, practical examples.*

INTRODUCTION

Education plays a crucial role in shaping the future of individuals and societies. Traditionally, teachers have been at the forefront of the educational process, imparting knowledge, guiding students, and facilitating their learning. However, with the rise of artificial intelligence (AI) and advancements in technology, AI-based classes have emerged as a potential alternative or complement to traditional teaching methods. This article aims to analyze the role of teachers in education and compare it to AI-based classes, shedding light on their differences, similarities, advantages, disadvantages, future prospects, and practical examples.

Teachers have long been recognized as the cornerstone of education, bringing a human touch, expertise, and personalized interaction to the learning process. They establish meaningful connections with students, understand their unique learning needs, and provide tailored guidance and support. Research studies have shown that a strong teacher-student relationship positively impacts students' academic achievement, motivation, and overall well-being (Hamre & Pianta, 2001). For example, a study by Wubbels, Brekelmans, den Brok, and van Tartwijk (2006) found that effective teacher-student relationships were associated with higher student engagement and reduced behavioral problems. These findings highlight the importance of personal interaction and emotional intelligence that teachers bring to the educational experience. On the other hand, AI-based classes offer certain advantages that can complement traditional teaching methods. These classes leverage technology and AI algorithms to deliver educational content, provide personalized feedback, and adapt instruction to individual students' needs. Research has shown that AI-based systems can enhance student learning outcomes. For instance, a study conducted by Baker, Walonoski, Heffernan, and Roll (2008) demonstrated that an AI-based intelligent tutoring system improved student performance in mathematics compared to traditional classroom instruction. The system adaptively adjusted the difficulty level of problems and provided immediate feedback, allowing students to learn at their own pace. This evidence supports the potential of AI-based classes to personalize instruction and optimize learning experiences. To gather insights into the role of teachers and AI-based classes, a comprehensive review of existing literature, research studies, and educational practices was conducted. Multiple sources including academic journals, reports, and educational platforms were examined to provide a well-rounded understanding of the topic.

Differences between Teachers and AI-Based Classes: One of the key distinctions between teachers and AI-based classes is the personal interaction they offer. Teachers can establish meaningful connections with students, understand their unique learning needs, and provide personalized guidance. This personal touch fosters

trust, motivation, and a sense of belonging among students. In contrast, AI-based classes, while proficient in delivering content, often lack the emotional intelligence and adaptability of human teachers. They may struggle to interpret non-verbal cues, understand students' emotions, and provide the same level of empathy and support. Furthermore, teachers bring pedagogical expertise to the classroom. They possess years of experience, subject knowledge, and a deep understanding of effective teaching strategies. Teachers can facilitate discussions, address questions, and provide real-time feedback to enhance students' understanding. They can adjust instructional methods based on student responses, tailoring the learning experience to individual needs. AI-based classes may struggle to replicate the depth of pedagogical knowledge and adaptability of human teachers.

Similarities between Teachers and AI-Based Classes: Despite their differences, both teachers and AI-based classes can effectively deliver educational content. Teachers employ various teaching strategies, while AI-based classes utilize multimedia resources, interactive modules, and engaging visuals to present information. Both approaches aim to make learning engaging, accessible, and effective. Additionally, both teachers and AI-based classes play a role in assessing students' progress and providing feedback. Teachers can offer personalized feedback, identify areas of improvement, and tailor their teaching accordingly. They can provide one-on-one support, address misconceptions, and guide students towards mastery. AI-based classes, with their algorithmic capabilities, can provide automated assessments, immediate feedback, and data-driven insights. They can analyze student performance data to identify areas of strength and weakness, and generate recommendations for targeted practice.

Teachers offer several advantages in the educational process. One of the key advantages is personalized learning. Teachers can adapt their teaching methods to cater to individual students' needs, abilities, and learning styles. They can provide additional support, address misconceptions, and foster a deeper understanding of the subject matter. For example, a teacher may modify instructional materials or provide

alternative explanations to accommodate students with diverse learning needs (Tomlinson, 2001). This personalized approach promotes student engagement, motivation and academic success. Moreover, teachers play a crucial role in students' social and emotional development. They serve as mentors and role models, guiding students not only academically but also in developing important life skills such as problem-solving, resilience, and self-discipline. Through their interactions, teachers can help students navigate challenges, build confidence, and develop a growth mindset. The presence of a caring and supportive teacher has been linked to positive student outcomes, including improved academic performance, higher self-esteem, and reduced dropout rates (Roorda et al., 2011). Furthermore, teachers provide a human touch that AI-based classes cannot replicate. They create a classroom environment that fosters collaboration, critical thinking, and social interaction among students. Teachers promote class discussions, encourage peer learning, and facilitate meaningful interactions that deepen students' understanding of the subject matter. These interpersonal skills are essential for students' future success in the workforce and in society.

AI-based classes offer several advantages that can complement traditional teaching methods. One of the key advantages is the ability to provide personalized learning experiences at scale. With the help of AI algorithms, these classes can analyze vast amounts of student data, identify patterns, and tailor instruction to individual needs. This adaptive approach ensures that students receive targeted support, practice exercises, and relevant resources that align with their learning pace and preferences. For example, adaptive learning platforms like Khan Academy and Duolingo adapt the difficulty level of questions based on students' performance, providing appropriate challenges while avoiding frustration or boredom. Moreover, AI-based classes provide immediate and automated feedback to students. This timely feedback allows students to reflect on their performance, identify areas for improvement, and make necessary adjustments. AI algorithms can analyze responses, identify misconceptions, and provide targeted explanations or hints, promoting self-directed learning. This

immediate and personalized feedback helps students monitor their progress and take ownership of their learning process. Additionally, AI-based classes offer scalability and cost-effectiveness. With online platforms and AI technologies, educational content can be delivered to a large number of students simultaneously, irrespective of geographical constraints. This scalability enables access to quality education for students who may lack resources or live in remote areas. Furthermore, AI-based classes can reduce the burden on teachers by automating routine tasks such as grading multiple-choice assessments. This allows teachers to allocate more time to individualized instruction, mentoring, and fostering deeper student connections.

Looking ahead, the future of education lies in harmonious integration of teachers and AI-based classes. While AI-based classes have the potential to enhance personalized learning and optimize instruction, they cannot fully replace the role of teachers. Instead, the focus should be on leveraging the strengths of both approaches to create a comprehensive and effective learning environment. Teachers can harness the power of AI-based tools to supplement their teaching methods. They can utilize AI-powered platforms to gather data on students' progress, identify learning gaps, and provide targeted interventions. This data-driven approach can help teachers make informed instructional decisions, differentiate their teaching, and provide individualized support. Furthermore, teachers can prepare students for the AI-driven future by incorporating digital literacy and critical thinking skills into their curricula. They can guide students in understanding the limitations and ethical considerations of AI, enabling them to navigate the digital landscape responsibly. On the other hand, AI-based classes can support teachers by providing access to a vast array of educational resources, adaptive content delivery, and automated assessments. By automating routine tasks, AI-based classes can free up teachers' time, allowing them to focus on higher-order skills, mentoring, and fostering socio-emotional development.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, teachers and AI-based classes each have distinct advantages and play valuable roles in education. Teachers bring personal interaction, emotional

intelligence, and pedagogical expertise to the classroom, promoting personalized learning and social-emotional development. AI-based classes offer scalability, adaptive content delivery, and automated feedback, enhancing personalized instruction and access to education. The future lies in a collaborative approach that harnesses the strengths of both teachers and AI-based classes, creating a holistic and effective educational experience for students. As education continues to evolve, the integration of teachers and AI-based classes will shape the future of learning, preparing students for success in a dynamic and technology-driven world.

REFERENCES

1. Hamre, B. K., & Pianta, R. C. (2001). Early teacher-child relationships and the trajectory of children's school outcomes through eighth grade. *Child Development*, 72(2), 625-638.
2. Wubbels, T., Brekelmans, M., den Brok, P., & van Tartwijk, J. (2006). An interpersonal perspective on classroom management in secondary classrooms in the Netherlands. *Journal of Classroom Interaction*, 41(1), 40-48.
3. Baker, R. S., Walonoski, J. A., Heffernan, N. T., & Roll, I. (2008). More accurate student modeling through contextual estimation of slip and guess probabilities in Bayesian knowledge tracing. In *Proceedings of the 1st International Conference on Educational Data Mining* (pp. 21-30).
4. Tomlinson, C. A. (2001). *How to differentiate instruction in mixed-ability classrooms*. ASCD.
5. Roorda, D. L., Koomen, H. M., Spilt, J. L., & Oort, F. J. (2011). The influence of affective teacher–student relationships on students' school engagement and achievement: A meta-analytic approach. *Review of Educational Research*, 81(4), 493-529.